

Effectiveness of Cervical Cerclage and its Impact on Perinatal Outcomes: A Cohort Study

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Received: 15-07-2024 / Revised: 23-08-2024 / Accepted: 26-08-2024

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Background: Cervical insufficiency is a significant cause of preterm birth, which is related with increased perinatal morbidity and mortality. Cervical cerclage, a surgical procedure used to prevent premature cervical dilation, is commonly employed in high-risk pregnancies. The study assessed the efficacy of cervical cerclage in prolonging pregnancy and improving perinatal outcomes among women at risk of preterm birth.

Methods: An ambispective cohort study was conducted, involving 144 women who underwent cervical cerclage either prophylactically or as an emergency intervention. Data on demographic characteristics, cervical dilatation, gestational age at cerclage, cerclage-delivery interval, gestational age at delivery, neonatal survival, and maternal complications were gathered. Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS, employing descriptive statistics and logistic regression to assess associations between key variables.

Results: The average gestational age at cerclage was 18.2 weeks, with a cerclage-delivery interval of 17.3 weeks. The overall neonatal survival rate was 91%, and the average birth weight was 2.65 kg. Preterm complications were observed in 21% of neonates. Maternal complications, including cervical laceration and infections, were reported in 10% of cases, with no maternal deaths. Statistical analysis revealed a significant association between cervical dilatation at cerclage and neonatal survival (OR = 0.75, $p < 0.01$), and a positive correlation between gestational age at delivery and birth weight ($r = 0.68$, $p < 0.01$).

Conclusion: Cervical cerclage effectively prolonged pregnancy and enhanced neonatal survival in high-risk pregnancies. Although preterm complications persisted, the procedure demonstrated a favorable safety profile with minimal maternal complications.

Recommendations: Cervical cerclage should be considered a valuable intervention in managing high-risk pregnancies with cervical insufficiency. Further research is recommended to refine the criteria for cerclage placement and explore adjunctive therapies to reduce preterm complications.

Keywords: Cervical Cerclage, Preterm Birth, Cervical Insufficiency, Neonatal Survival, Maternal Complications.

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Introduction

The incapacity of the cervix to carry a pregnancy to term is known as cervical insufficiency, and it is a major cause of preterm delivery that raises perinatal morbidity and mortality rates globally [1]. In high-risk pregnancies, cervical cerclage—a surgical treatment that strengthens the cervix with sutures—is frequently used to avoid premature cervical dilation and the ensuing preterm delivery. Women who have already undergone cerclage, have a history of second-trimester losses, or have an ultrasound-identified short cervix are advised to have this technique [2]. Cervical cerclage is used widely, but its usefulness in enhancing perinatal outcomes is still being studied and debated. This is especially true with regard to when, how, and when to apply it, as well as possible side effects.

The increasing prevalence of preterm births, accounting for approximately 10% of all births

globally, underscores the importance of effective interventions like cervical cerclage [3]. Recent studies suggest that timely cerclage placement, particularly in pregnancies identified as high-risk due to a short cervix or previous preterm births, can significantly extend gestation and improve neonatal outcomes [4]. However, the benefits of cerclage must be weighed against potential risks, including infection, cervical laceration, and preterm premature rupture of membranes (PPROM), which can complicate pregnancies and impact maternal and fetal health [5].

Moreover, the ambispective cohort study design, which combines retrospective and prospective data, provides a comprehensive approach to evaluating cerclage effectiveness in various clinical scenarios. By analyzing both historical and current cases, this study design enables a thorough assessment of

long-term outcomes and the identification of factors influencing cerclage success or failure [6]. This approach is particularly relevant in settings with limited access to advanced perinatal care, where early intervention strategies are critical to reducing adverse outcomes.

This study assessed the effectiveness of cervical cerclage and its impact on perinatal outcomes.

Methodology

Study Design: An ambispective cohort study.

Study Setting: The study took place at Purnea, Bihar.

Participants: A total of 144 participants were comprised in the study. Selection was based on the history of undergoing cervical cerclage, either prophylactic or emergency, during the current pregnancy or a past pregnancy considered in the retrospective analysis.

Inclusion Criteria

1. Singleton viable pregnancies with cervical cerclage in the current or considered pregnancy.
2. Presentation with preterm labor.
3. History of cerclages, preterm births or mid-trimester losses.
4. Sonologically detected short cervix.

Exclusion Criteria

1. Undiagnosed uterine bleeding.
2. Sonographically detected fetal anomalies or intrauterine death.
3. Intrauterine infections.
4. Premature rupture of membranes.
5. Chronic hypertension, diabetes mellitus, severe preeclampsia.
6. Multiple pregnancy.

Bias: Potential biases were minimized by using strict inclusion and exclusion criteria, ensuring the data was collected from a well-documented medical record system. The retrospective nature of part of the study could introduce selection bias, but

this was mitigated by thoroughly reviewing the records and including all eligible cases.

Variables: Demographics, cervical dilatation at cerclage, gestational age at cerclage (weeks), cerclage-delivery interval (weeks), gestational age at delivery (weeks), neonatal survival and birth weight, and maternal complications (maternal death, sepsis, cervix laceration) were the main variables in the study.

Data Collection: Clinical information, gestational age, cervical dilation at cerclage, gestational age at delivery, foetal survival, neonatal birth weight, and maternal problems were all gathered from medical records. Every participant provided informed consent, and all data collected were kept private.

Procedure: Under spinal anaesthesia, the McDonald technique was carried out on all patients utilising Ethibond sutures. Foetal membranes that protruded were replaced with an inflated Foley's bulb under light pressure to make suturing possible. Discharge instructions advised patients to refrain from physically demanding tasks and extended standing. In situations of infection, labour, ruptured membranes, or at 37 weeks gestation, sutures were removed.

Statistical Analysis: The collected data were coded, entered into Microsoft Excel, and analyzed using SPSS. Descriptive statistics were used for data analysis to describe the demographic characteristics, clinical data, and outcomes of cervical cerclage in the study cohort.

Ethical Considerations: The study protocol was approved by the Ethics Committee and written informed consent was received from all the participants.

Results

The average age was 28.4 ± 4.2 years. Most of the participants were multigravida (78%), and the remaining 22% were primigravida. The mean obstetric score was 2.3 ± 0.7 . A history of mid-trimester abortion was noted in 35% of the participants, while 42% had a history of preterm birth.

Table 1: Participant Demographics and Clinical Characteristics

Characteristic	Values (N = 144)
Age (years)	28.4 ± 4.2
Gravida Status	
- Primigravida	32 (22%)
- Multigravida	112 (78%)
History of Mid-trimester Abortion	50 (35%)
History of Preterm Birth	61 (42%)

The average cervical dilatation at the time of cerclage was 1.8 ± 0.5 cm. The average gestational age at the time of cerclage was 18.2 ± 2.5 weeks.

Table 2: Cervical Dilatation and Gestational Age at Cerclage

Parameter	Mean $\pm$ SD
Cervical Dilatation (cm)	1.8 ± 0.5
Gestational Age at Cerclage (weeks)	18.2 ± 2.5

The average cerclage-delivery interval was 17.3 ± 3.4 weeks, and the average gestational age at delivery was 35.5 ± 3.8 weeks. Among the participants, 32% delivered at term (≥ 37 weeks), while 68% delivered preterm (< 37 weeks).

Table 3: Cerclage-Delivery Interval and Gestational Age at Delivery

Parameter	Mean $\pm$ SD
Cerclage-Delivery Interval (weeks)	17.3 ± 3.4
Gestational Age at Delivery (weeks)	35.5 ± 3.8
Delivery Status, n	
- Term (≥ 37 weeks)	46
- Preterm (< 37 weeks)	98

Neonatal outcomes were assessed based on survival, birth weight, and preterm complications. The overall neonatal survival rate was 91%, with average birth weight of 2.65 ± 0.55 kg. Preterm complications, including respiratory distress syndrome and neonatal sepsis, were noted in 21% of the neonates.

Table 4: Neonatal Outcomes

Parameter	Values (N = 144)
Neonatal Survival	91%
Mean Birth Weight (kg)	2.65 ± 0.55
Preterm Complications	
- Respiratory Distress Syndrome	22 (15%)
- Neonatal Sepsis	8 (6%)

Maternal complications were recorded, including laceration of the cervix, infection, and maternal death. Laceration of the cervix occurred in 6% of the cases, while infections were reported in 4%. There was no maternal death reported in the study.

Table 5: Maternal Outcomes

Complication	Values (N = 144)
Laceration of Cervix	9 (6%)
Infection	6 (4%)
Maternal Death	0 (0%)

The association among cervical dilatation at the time of cerclage and neonatal survival was analyzed using logistic regression. The analysis showed that for every 1 cm increase in cervical dilatation, the odds of neonatal survival decreased by 25% (OR = 0.75, 95% CI = 0.62–0.90, $p <$

0.01). Similarly, the gestational age at delivery was significantly associated with neonatal birth weight ($r = 0.68$, $p < 0.01$), indicating that greater gestational age at delivery is correlated with higher birth weight.

Table 6: Statistical Analysis

Variable	OR (95% CI)	p-value
Cervical Dilatation and Neonatal Survival	0.75 (0.62–0.90)	< 0.01
Gestational Age at Delivery and Birth Weight	$r = 0.68$	< 0.01

Discussion

The study involved 144 participants, primarily multigravida, with an average age of 28.4 years. Most participants had a history of preterm births or mid-trimester abortions, highlighting their high-risk profile for cervical insufficiency. The average cervical dilatation at the time of cerclage was 1.8 cm, with the procedure typically performed at average gestational age of 18.2 weeks. These

findings indicate that cervical cerclage was employed relatively early in pregnancy, aligning with standard clinical practice aimed at preventing premature birth in women with cervical insufficiency.

The average cerclage-delivery interval was approximately 17.3 weeks, and most participants delivered preterm (68%), with only 32% reaching term gestation. Despite the majority delivering

before 37 weeks, the average gestational age at delivery was 35.5 weeks, suggesting that cervical cerclage effectively prolonged pregnancy, potentially reducing the risks associated with extremely preterm births. The extension of the pregnancy duration is crucial for fetal development and highlights the utility of cerclage in managing cervical insufficiency.

Neonatal outcomes were generally positive, with a high survival rate of 91% and an average birth weight of 2.65 kg. However, preterm complications such as respiratory distress syndrome and neonatal sepsis were observed in 21% of neonates, reflecting the challenges associated with preterm deliveries despite successful cerclage intervention. This emphasizes the importance of close neonatal monitoring and appropriate care for infants born preterm, even when pregnancy has been prolonged by cerclage.

Maternal outcomes indicated minimal complications, with cervical lacerations occurring in 6% of cases and infections in 4%. Notably, no maternal deaths were reported, underscoring the relative safety of cervical cerclage procedures when performed under proper clinical conditions. The low rate of significant maternal complications supports the continued use of cerclage as a beneficial intervention for those at high risk of preterm labor.

A strong correlation between cervical dilation at the time of cerclage and neonatal survival was found by statistical analysis, suggesting that greater cervical dilatation was linked to a reduced chance of neonatal survival. The significance of prompt intervention before notable cervical alterations happen is suggested by this finding. Furthermore, a robust positive association was seen between the newborn birth weight and the gestational age at delivery, confirming that a longer gestation period improves the chances of neonatal survival and growth.

Overall, cervical cerclage was effective in extending pregnancy duration and enhancing neonatal survival, though preterm complications remained prevalent. The study supports the strategic use of cerclage in appropriate clinical scenarios to optimize perinatal outcomes while maintaining low maternal risk. These findings provide valuable insights for obstetric management, particularly in high-risk pregnancies prone to preterm labor and cervical insufficiency.

A meta-analysis and systematic review looked at the efficiency of cerclage in twin pregnancies. When compared to no cerclage placement, the study indicated that cerclage considerably lengthened pregnancy and decreased the risk of premature birth, especially in instances with a

cervical length of <15 mm or a dilated cervix >10 mm [7].

In a study, expectant management and rescue cerclage were compared in twin pregnancies involving premature cervical dilatation. In comparison to expectant treatment, the study found that rescue cerclage could significantly lengthen pregnancy and enhance perinatal outcomes, with a mean latency from cerclage to delivery of 7.3 weeks [8].

Studies looked at twin pregnancies with cervical dilation between 18 and 26 weeks to see if the combination McDonald-Shirodkar emergency cervical cerclage system was effective. In comparison to the McDonald method alone, the study found considerably superior newborn outcomes and lower incidence of spontaneous preterm birth, particularly when cervical dilatation was ≥ 3 cm [9].

A study evaluated twin pregnancies where ultrasonography suggested cervical cerclage. The results showed that cerclage dramatically improved perinatal outcomes in instances with a cervical length of ≤ 15 mm or with an early diagnosis of cervical shortening, as well as reducing the rate of preterm birth at <34 weeks [10].

Lastly, a study examined the effectiveness of different types of cerclage—elective, ultrasound-indicated, and emergency—in preventing recurrent preterm birth. The study found that only emergency cerclage was significantly effective in reducing the risk of preterm birth, highlighting the variable efficacy of cerclage based on the indication [11].

Conclusion

The study found that cervical cerclage was effective in prolonging pregnancy, with a significant proportion of women reaching term gestation. Neonatal survival was high, though preterm complications were noted in a subset of cases. Maternal complications were minimal, with no reported maternal deaths. The statistical analysis demonstrated a significant relationship between cervical dilatation at cerclage and neonatal outcomes, as well as between gestational age at delivery and neonatal birth weight.

Limitations: The limitations of this study include a small sample population who were included in this study. Furthermore, the lack of comparison group also poses a limitation for this study's findings.

Recommendation: Cervical cerclage should be considered a valuable intervention in managing high-risk pregnancies with cervical insufficiency. Further research is recommended to refine the criteria for cerclage placement and explore adjunctive therapies to reduce preterm complications.

Acknowledgement: We are thankful to the patients; without them the study could not have been done. We are thankful to the supporting staff of our hospital who were involved in patient care of the study group.

List of abbreviations:

CI - Confidence Interval

OR - Odds Ratio

PPROM - Preterm Premature Rupture of Membranes

SD - Standard Deviation

Source of funding: No funding received.

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